

CUSTOMER360 APPLICATION USING DATA ANALYTICAL STRATEGY FOR THE FINANCIAL SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This article provides an overview of the most important function that data analytics plays in the revolutionising of banking and financial services. The purpose of this study is to investigate the ways in which contemporary data platforms enable a comprehensive 360-degree view of customers, optimise loan processes through predictive analytics, boost corporate operations through automation, and provide personalised customer experiences among other benefits. By utilising advanced analytics, financial institutions can streamline their operations, enhance their decision-making processes, adhere to regulatory requirements, and create stronger relationships with their customers. Furthermore, this highlights the revolutionary influence that data-driven strategies have in terms of driving operational efficiency and strategic growth within the financial sector.

Keywords: Banking Industry, Customer Classification, Customer Segmentation, Data Mining, Data Analysis

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INTRODUCTION

Intelligent decision support systems in banking have been the subject of study for more than forty years. They developed a banking application-specific expert system for direct customer sales. However, knowledge-based models impacting management decision-making were lacking in most studies. In the early to mid-90s, data mining was employed by intelligent decision models to supplement standard banking procedures for insurance. However, even in the developed markets industry, such advancements only led to gradual progress. Using big data and AI for digital marketing, more recent efforts have concentrated on cross-selling and managerial decision-making. Combining AI with big data allows for intelligent marketing, and it has already cut technical inefficiencies for Indian banks by as much as 11% (Mor & Gupta, 2021) [1]. According to recent industry figures, 25% of new bank clients in the US switch providers within the first year, and 50% churn before 90 days.

Therefore, it begs the question: what went wrong? Possible causes include insufficient consumer data visibility, operational data silos, increased costs, and subpar customer experience. When it comes to digital sales preparedness, European countries including Spain, Poland, the Netherlands, and Australia are ahead of the curve, according to a 2019 analysis by the Boston Consulting Group. This includes the United States and Germany.

Despite the rise of e-banking in emerging economies, the choice dilemma surrounding its adoption among diverse business models calls for additional research into the topic's effectiveness (Gupta, Raychaudhuri & Haldar, 2018) [2]. New research shows that developing market adoption of West-centric service value scales is only mostly accurate (Roy, Paul, Quazi & Nguyen, 2018) [3]. The digital gap, which prevents financial services from achieving their sustainable goals, is accelerated when generalised assumptions are used (Katiyar & Badola, 2018;) [4]. Changes such as automated teller machines (ATMs) have reduced the need for human intervention in banking, which is good news for service providers (Huang & Rust, 2018) [5]. Therefore, figuring out the processes for effective banking information management is crucial. Practical investigations on the topic are few and far between (Hasheminejad & Khorrami, 2018) [6].

Two of the most important uses of marketing information systems (MkIS) in banking have been identified since the 1970s: client segmentation and cross-selling. Later, as the field progressed, scholars drew from a wide variety of interdisciplinary theories. Worldwide banking remained resilient, according to recent reports (Deloitte, 2019), but institutions show casual resistance to technology out of concern that expenses would lead to closure, insolvency, or mergers. Discovered that to improve data standards and bureaucracy in the Indian environment, banking activities must be run efficiently. Information systems research has also failed to adequately root the concepts, even though technology is crucial to the banking industry. Additionally, many algorithms and models from machine learning can help in decision-making (Kar & Dwivedi, 2020) [7]. In Finland, the adoption of mobile/internet banking is severely hindered by a value barrier. Therefore, we review the literature on several aspects of information management and technology. To have a full picture of the situation, we put ourselves in the shoes of both the service provider and the consumer.

1 P.C. (Personal computer) banking: The developed markets were the first to provide home banking through personal computers. A study involving four companies found that digital channel adoption leads to improved customer retention rates and more profits in the long run. P.C. banking gradually shifted its focus to different channels of service delivery in order to cater to clients who were less comfortable with technology.

2 E-banking (Electronic)/ Internet banking: There have been studies measuring things like customer loyalty and other indicators since the beginning. According to the results of this study, there is no discernible change in customer loyalty while banking online. Using elements from both TAM and TPB, the authors of these works proposed expanding TPB to include factors like perceived benefit and perceived risk. Customers' individuality and the brand's standing also matter greatly (Marakarkandy, Yajnik & Dasgupta, 2017) [8]. Karjaluoto, Shaikh, Saarijärvi, and Saraniemi (2019) [9] present research on mobile banking in Finland that highlights the importance of better management benefits for banks that make investments in these areas. The Australian environment was also used to study the behaviour after adoption. Customers were impacted by technology, channel, and value-for-money, according to their research. Social considerations had minimal bearing on the decision-making process, which goes against common sense. Another finding from neural network modelling is that the perceived ease of use is a major external risk for online banking acceptability in emerging economies like India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A variety of theoretical perspectives have contributed to the development of banking information management as a field. Banking industries found I.S. alignment to be vital, and empirical studies have highlighted its importance in developed markets (Reynolds & Yetton, 2015) [10]. Next, we looked at intelligent decision support models from the viewpoints of information systems, marketing, and business process reengineering. When it comes to creativity, efficiency, and strategic objectives, I.T. acts as a moderator between organisational variables. Similarly, summarised the information technology needs of the organisation by investigating several aspects of the customer-organization interaction. According to the TAM framework, internet banking behavioural intention is negatively affected by risk. The most significant factors that hinder business-IT alignment include waiting for tasks to be completed, not having enough time to learn new information, not having enough cross-sectional training, depending on telecom operators, banking staff having a heavy workload, and being hesitant to hire more people. Listed below are the five most popular articles published in the past ten years:

- A model for mobile banking user adoption was proposed by Kushwaha, Kar, and Dwivedi (2021) [11] (Google scholar TC=1460, per year: 61.64). This model combined Task technology fit (TTF) with the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT).
- In a case study at a Slovenian bank, according to Sharma, Deb, and Maitra (2021) [12] (Google Scholar TC= 1271, per year: 45.73), a crucial success factor is the standardisation of processes, information, and automation, as well as the training and empowerment of staff. The framework was tested using the UTAUT model and perceived risk factor by Rana, Luthra, and Rao (2019) (Google Scholar total citations T.C.: 1147, per year: 72.71). Discovered that the inclination to use online banking is significantly predicted by perceived risk.

- Lagna and Ravishankar (2021) [13] (yearly average of 57.5 G.S. citations = 817). The review article pointed out that the assessment of 55 empirical works did not provide a roadmap for the growth of mobile banking. Jiménez-Márquez, López-Cuadrado, and Ruiz-Mezcua (2019) [14] are the authors of the study. The causes that hinder the adoption of mobile banking were investigated (G.S. scholar TC= 327, per year: 12.64), and it was discovered that banks' help and guidance decreased the usage barrier. Additionally crucial were the image, value, and use-related risk.

Intelligent procedures and information technology (IT) help business users make decisions when organisations investigate Next Best Offer (NBO) agreements. In most cases, the manager will receive input from the zonal level, the regional level, and the branch offices regarding the sales objective that follows the marketing plan. The ability or burden of branch/division managers to engage in direct exchanges that lead to the cross-selling of insurance products is limited. Perceived utility (P.U.), perceived ease of use (PEOU), trust, and technical self-efficacy (TSE) were determined to have a significant impact on user acceptance of online banking information systems (OBIS) in emerging economies. A number of recent studies have successfully used machine learning to analyse insurance claims (Rawat, Rawat, Kumar & Sabitha, 2021) [15].

OVERVIEW OF CUSTOMER360 APPLICATION

What is a 360-Degree Customer View?

One complete picture of a customer's data is a 360-degree customer view. Some examples of the types of data collected from customers include their basic contact details, purchase history (both current and historical), and details about their interactions with various business touchpoints throughout their journey.

Businesses can provide the greatest possible customer experience across unified channels and touchpoints by incorporating customisation, made possible by 360-degree customer views and the quantity of data they contain.

Why do I Need a 360-Customer View? 4 Benefits

Businesses may greatly benefit from 360-degree customer perspectives. One way they bring value is by helping organisations improve their marketing strategies. This, in turn, reduces costs and develops profitable relationships with customers through customisation. Here are four key advantages:

1. Predictive Analytics

Customer perspectives from every angle Analyse past client action to anticipate their future actions. Making a thorough profile of a customer helps companies anticipate their needs. Companies may take advantage of cross-sell, churn, and up-sell opportunities with the help of this higher-quality predictive research and data. If these predictive audiences are to be effective, machine learning will be heavily involved. As a bonus, it enables these audiences to be lightning fast, ultra precise, and scalable. As a bonus, it helps businesses plan by showing them where and how they may modify their service offerings based on customer behaviour predictions, which in turn helps them lessen the blow of future changes.

2. Enhanced Personalisation

By utilising 360-degree consumer views, businesses can greatly improve their ability to provide tailored experiences. Better personalised and relevant product recommendations are possible with a comprehensive view of a consumer that includes all of their browsing and purchase behaviour. Having this advantage allows firms to connect with customers on a deeper level, fostering trust and establishing lasting connections. As a result, client loyalty is enhanced, which in turn decreases customer turnover and increases lifetime order values (LTVs) thanks to strong ties.

3. Improved Customer Experiences

A 360-degree customer view's capacity to foster improved customer experiences is, in the end, one of its most significant advantages. Many companies make the mistake of basing future client interactions solely on data collected from their most recent engagement with the customer. However, because it disregards pertinent transactions and prior encounters, this does not give a whole view of their connection. Therefore, the experience it provides is disjointed and useless. A significant portion of service agents, specifically 42%, frequently cite inaccessible or incomplete client data as the primary cause of their inability to effectively resolve customer complaints. This data silosity leads to disjointed experiences for customers. Both problems are avoided with 360-degree customer views since all the client's data is kept in one central area that is accessible from any tool or department. As a result, customers are better satisfied because of a more tailored experience.

4. Complete Cross-Department Customer Alignment

Lastly, a 360-degree customer view can help improve customer alignment across departments by bringing together marketing, sales, and service. The customer's journey through the company is made to feel seamless when departments share a holistic perspective of the client. This implies that vital information can be easily accessed and passed along. As a result, the marketing and sales departments are free to construct data-driven, smart campaigns that leverage the information gleaned from the 360-degree customer view. Just by coordinating their

efforts, marketing and sales may increase revenue by 32% and client retention by 36%, according to the research.

HOW TO BUILD A 360 CUSTOMER VIEW

Data Audit

Accurate and meaningful insights can be achieved using high-quality data. To make this a reality, it is crucial to maintain well-organized and clean data. A data audit can help with this. To begin an audit, it is necessary to establish a procedure whereby all departments input their data consistently and in an easily comprehensible format. For future efficiency gains, it is best if the consistency holds true across all the systems in use, both now and in the past. Although laborious, this process of regularly inputting each piece of data guarantees correctness and relevance due to correlations between apparently unrelated bits (for example, two seemingly unrelated people could have same interests).

Use a Customer Data Platform (CDP)

Customer data platforms (CDPs) do double duty: they compile and manage customer data gathered from various touchpoints, build centralised profiles of each customer, and make that data accessible to other systems, software, and MarTech stacks. Consequently, the manual data audit that was discussed earlier is practically rendered unnecessary with a CDP. By integrating data from multiple sources, including first-, second-, and third-party sources, CDPs construct thorough profiles of their clients. That implies they may compile and arrange information from your customer relationship management system (CRM), data warehouse (DMP), emails, social media, transactional systems, website (including cookies, forms, and eCommerce behavioural actions), and more to provide you a complete picture of your clients.

Social Listening Tools

Researching consumer habits through social media is highly effective. Social data, in contrast to more conventional marketing metrics, provides raw, unfiltered insights into the sociological characteristics and behaviours of your target audience as it relates to societal trends. This allows businesses to have a deeper understanding of their customers' sentiments on specific changes in attitude and behaviour brought about by external factors. Additionally, a potent instrument for business growth might be evaluating customer features such as shopping and browsing trends in conjunction with social media activity. For instance, your company can benefit from data that shows how customers' opinions are shifting about a product or service they're using. This allows you to adjust before your target audience loses interest in what you have to offer.

Examples of a 360 Customer View

Bringing together marketing interactions and transaction data is one way to implement a 360-customer view. As soon as a user lands on a website, they start to establish a profile through various customer touchpoints like social media engagements, form fills, and product page clicks. You can take it a step further with Zeotap's Customer Data Platform. Unknown website visitors can be identified before they engage with your touchpoints by combining this information with additional data. Because of this, companies may move swiftly to convert leads into paying clients, which increases their revenue.

After that, data enrichment would add demographic or geographic layers to the primary consumer data, making the raw data even more valuable. With additional data, we can learn more about the customer's life, which makes it easier to tailor our offerings to their unique preferences.

A comprehensive, 360-degree perspective of the consumer is generated when the original data acquired from the client through their interactions is combined with enhanced data from third parties. To increase the likelihood of a sale, tailored messaging can be sent to customers based on this aggregated data, which can be accessed, edited, and shared across several departments.

Closing Thoughts

Customers' expectations are always evolving, and businesses must be flexible enough to meet them. Personalised experiences are becoming increasingly important to customers, and firms that fail to establish genuine connections with them will struggle to compete. By analysing customer feedback from all angles, businesses can learn from their successes and areas for growth. This, in turn, improves customer journeys and experiences, which in turn raises the likelihood of long-term client retention.

Customer intelligence, retention, and knowledge may all be enhanced with the use of data and a 360-degree view. With this, you may improve customer intelligence and operational efficiency using predictive analytics across all digital platforms and marketing activities. With the help of CDPs, businesses can see the big picture and make sure they are thinking about every step of the customer journey. Providing an inclusive experience through the tracking of all customer contacts (big or small) makes customers loyal, which in turn increases the likelihood that they will buy from you again and tell their friends about your business.

REVOLUTIONIZING FINANCIAL SERVICES: AI AND ML-DRIVEN CUSTOMER 360 AND PERSONALIZATION

The financial services industry is vital to our everyday lives since they assist us with managing our money, buying a house, and saving for retirement. With a vast array of products and services to choose from, including loans, credit cards, insurance, investment management, and payment processing, the sector streamlines intricate financial activities and ensures they are accessible to all. Consequently, adopting a 360° customer view driven by artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) is more crucial than ever before for innovative BFSI organisations. Client demands and expectations in the financial services sector are dynamic and ever-changing. To give the best possible service, financial service providers must have a deep understanding of their clients' wants, needs, and habits. Achieving this goal in the era of big data and AI requires data-driven consumer intelligence and customisation. Essentially, a 360° customer view provides a comprehensive picture of customers by integrating data from many sources to paint a full picture of their profile, including their identifying information, account details, behaviours, preferences, and needs. Financial service providers can better meet their clients' demands by diving into this data to learn more about their specific preferences and requirements. The result can be more revenue and customer loyalty because of happier customers and better overall experiences.

Not only that, but a 360° customer view helps businesses comprehend their customers' journeys better, beginning with the first point of contact and continuing through all subsequent encounters. By gaining this knowledge, financial service companies can enhance their sales and marketing efforts, streamline their client acquisition process, and implement more efficient tactics for engagement and retention.

What follows is an expanded discussion of the reasons why the financial services sector would do well to adopt a 360-degree client view.

Why is there a Need for 360° Customer Views in the BFSI Industry?

Many different types of companies and organisations provide various financial products and services to people, companies, and governments; this broad and complex sector is known as the financial services industry. Countless other types of businesses fall under this category, such as banks, credit unions, investment agencies, insurance providers, accounting and tax services, financial planning businesses, and many more. By acting as a go-between for investors and borrowers, the financial services sector plays an essential role in the world economy. Processing payments, lending money, managing investments, risk, and insurance are all essential services provided by financial organisations. Financial service companies must ensure client satisfaction and loyalty because providing these services requires a high degree of trust and confidence from customers. Consequently, a customer 360° and personalisation strategy driven by AI and ML is a powerful weapon these providers may employ to guarantee client happiness and loyalty.

In-Depth Analysis of Customer Data

Financial institutions have access to mountains of client data, but not all of it is helpful for determining what those customers need. Here is where the Next Best Action Model and consumer intelligence come into play. Banks and other financial institutions can use predictive analytics and modelling technologies to augment the main data stored on internal servers with data collected from external communication channels. Customer intelligence and analytics platform solutions developed by Grid Dynamics include both primary and secondary sources of data into statistical models used for lead scoring. Transactional systems, marketing automation software, and external advertising platforms can all be seamlessly integrated with these solutions. Some examples of first-party data include demographic information (such as age, income, and occupation) and details about the customer's plan or account members, up to and including their family members. The information gathered by third parties may include information from social media platforms, online shopping histories, and Internet of Things (IoT) sensor data. Financial service providers can automate their daily decision-making process for customer acquisition and retention and deliver more personalised user interaction by optimising this data in a customer 360° perspective. For better customer retention rates, risk analysis, fraud detection, and message targeting, AI and ML systems may also detect geopolitical events, weather signals, competitor actions, market trends, and behavioural patterns. Financial service providers may boost revenue, satisfy customers more, and strengthen relationships by concentrating on what they do best and it is shown in figure 1.

Fig 1: Customer various analysis on banking.

Customer Satisfaction

Customers need to have a lot of faith in their supplier when they apply for big financial products like mortgages, loans, and insurance. Consumers may grow dissatisfied and contemplate going elsewhere for their business if they encounter excessively difficult or ambiguous processes or if they do not receive adequate customer service. Furthermore, customers anticipate swift resolution of their concerns, easy access to their account information, and timely responses to their inquiries and requests. To keep customers coming back, earn their trust, and keep their business, customer service must be a top priority.

Customers need competent and compassionate support from financial service providers to successfully manage the complicated goods and services they offer. Providers of financial services also need to be prepared to deal with data breaches, fraud, and identity theft in a timely and proactive manner. Problems like these, if left unattended, can ruin a business's image and drive away customers. Prioritising customer care and growing client loyalty can help financial service providers beat their competition in the long run. Streamlining claims processing and service delivery is crucial for financial service providers to be competitive in today's fast-paced digital world. An automated, omnichannel platform where users can submit claims, complaints, and service requests is one viable option. Simplified administration of policies and accounts is now possible for customers through their preferred channels and on any device. By consolidating this information into one place, financial service providers can see the big picture of their customers' needs and help agents address their questions and concerns more quickly and effectively. Targeted marketing and sales strategies can be developed with this data to boost customer loyalty and retention rates and that are shown in figure 2. In the end, an automated omnichannel strategy boosts customer satisfaction, makes it easier for customers to submit claims or applications, and makes customer support personnel more efficient and successful. Customer happiness, brand loyalty, and financial success in the long run are all outcomes of this.

Fig 2: Use Cases of Banking Chatbots.

AI-Driven Workflows

Conversational AI systems allow users to communicate with virtual assistants and get relevant information using deep natural language processing skills. With the data stored and processed by the system, it can retrieve information using structured queries and semantic searches. Regardless of their location, clients may access detailed and pertinent information at any time thanks to this. The conversational AI system learns from its customers' interactions and improves its ability to cater to their demands with more precise and tailored responses.

Personal Finance Management

There are a variety of ways in which the financial services sector might reap the benefits of AI-driven workflows. Implementing virtual assistants to assist consumers with managing their personal finances is one example of such a use case. Financial advisors can better serve their clients by tailoring recommendations and guidance to everyone's unique situation, spending habits, risk tolerance, and financial objectives with the help of artificial intelligence. Customers are then able to make more educated judgements and improve their financial management as a result.

Fraud Detection and Prevention

Financial organisations can benefit from AI's ability to monitor transactions and flag questionable activity to reduce losses caused by fraud. Also, by analysing data and market patterns, AI assistants can help financial institutions spot and reduce portfolio risks, keep an eye on credit and market concerns, and spot new hazards as they emerge.

Customer Service

Aside from manufacturing, AI has the potential to revolutionise customer service. Chatbots powered by artificial intelligence may assist consumers around the clock, answer frequently asked questions, shorten wait times at call centres, and boost satisfaction levels. Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionise investment management by providing insightful market data in real-time and tailoring recommendations to each client's unique investing profile and preferences.

For companies in the Fortune 1000, Grid Dynamics is the go-to provider of conversational AI solutions. To apply deep learning techniques and construct custom language models relevant to your company's domain, our developers make use of open-source software frameworks like TensorFlow or PyTorch. Whether you are in the banking sector or some other, this will make sure that your conversational AI system knows your clientele and what they require. Google Home, Amazon Echo, Facebook Messenger, and other similar systems can also work with the conversational AI system.

What is Needed to Achieve a Customer 360° View?

Building a consumer 360-degree vision could be challenging for financial services organisations, but there are plenty of resources to help. Platforms for processing and analysing data are essential; these include the Next Best Action Model, omnichannel user experiences, conversational AI models, and the Grid Dynamics Analytics Platform and Machine Learning Platform.

Grid Dynamics Analytics and Machine Learning Platforms

Banking, insurance, and financial services organisations can consolidate client data from disparate sources with the help of analytics and machine learning platforms. With the platform's extensive analytics and data visualisation features, it is much simpler to spot patterns and trends that can lead to happier and more satisfied customers. Grid Dynamics knows that to know their customers inside and out, they need a solid data platform. For businesses that rely heavily on data, we have developed AWS and Google Cloud Analytics Platform Starter Kits based on our extensive knowledge of cloud computing, machine learning, and data analytics. Our technologies streamline the execution of 360-degree consumer views, improve data accessibility and quality, and expedite insights and these differences are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Difference between Google Cloud Platform and Amazon Web Services.

Google Cloud Platform	Amazon Web Services
Analytics Platform Starter Kit for GCP	Analytics Platform Starter Kit for AWS
Machine Learning Platform Starter Kit for GCP	Machine Learning Platform Starter Kit for AWS

Many banks and other financial institutions still use antiquated methods of data storage, such as on-premise EDW software, which hinders future technical developments and scalability. Grid Dynamics can assist you in moving your data to the cloud, where it will be more efficiently and scalable. Gain an advantage in cutthroat marketplaces by optimising data-driven procedures.

360 Degree Customer View Financial Services: Summing up

Companies in the BFSI business can give customers what they want—personalized experiences—by using data-driven customer intelligence, a customer 360° strategy, and personalisation. Financial service providers may optimise their offerings, boost customer happiness and loyalty, and drive revenue growth with a complete picture of clients' preferences and behaviours. To successfully acquire and retain customers, as well as to design efficient marketing and sales strategies, it is essential to have a deep understanding of customer journeys. If you want to keep your financial services competitive, you need to adopt a 360-degree consumer view.

USE CASES OF DATA ANALYTICS IN BANKING AND FINANCIAL SERVICES

A 360-Degree Customer View

One of the most desired features of a data platform is the ability to see the customer from every angle. This is because, as stated in Accenture's 2023 report, a large majority of global executives (83%) think that having a single customer perspective is essential for providing personalised experiences.

The bank can create comprehensive customer profiles that mirror its primary areas of concentration by storing and periodically updating client information on the data platform. Put simply, it offers a holistic view of the client by incorporating data from many sources. Important customer data, including interests, marital status, possible financial product interest, and marketing campaign answers, is stored in a customer relationship management system. At the same time, the card system keeps tabs on customers' spending habits, and when integrated with core banking, it provides banks with information about customers' credit, current accounts, deposits, securities, and more.

When banks have a complete view of their customers' behaviours, they can better target their marketing to provide customers with the products and services they want, be it a savings account, credit card, concierge service, or insurance for their car or trip. Sales and marketing teams find customer data most useful for targeting specific demographics with more personalised and engaging sales pitches.

Optimized Loan Process

To streamline the loan process, which includes loan origination, servicing, collections, risk management, and reporting, a data platform is used. This platform acts as a central repository for all data-related to lending. Forty percent of mortgage and loan origination process participants intend to use data platforms, according to a MongoDB-commissioned study.

Fig 3: Top Data Analytics Use Cases in Banking & Fintech

Data platforms use sophisticated algorithms to sift through mountains of historical data from places like credit bureau records, thanks to the integration of machine learning and big data analytics. Based on the customer's credit history and other criteria, these analyses provide models that can estimate the appropriate loan amount. Additionally, within a specific time frame following its closure or disbursement, this type of model may forecast the likelihood of default on loans, if any.

All things considered, data platforms improve loan distribution by automating the whole process, which in turn makes it quicker and more efficient. Some more benefits are also brought about by their implementation:

Reduced paperwork and manual errors. Reduced reliance on paper documents and human data entry is one benefit of digital process streamlining that improves accuracy and reduces the likelihood of mistakes.

Better customer experience. An enhanced client experience is directly attributable to quicker processing times, clearer communication, and customised lending possibilities.

Regulatory compliance. Since data platforms guarantee data security and have a centralised audit trail, they make regulatory compliance easier.

Adopting Data Analytics Tools

- The real worth of the data platform comes from the insights it provides, which allow decision-makers to optimise plans and produce measurable business outcomes from raw data. The McKinsey Global Institute found that companies who use analytics to their advantage can be up to 10% more profitable than their competitors. In order to gain clear and relevant insights on consumer behaviour, tastes, and market trends, cutting-edge analytical tools process massive datasets in real-time. With this new knowledge, decision-makers can:

Enhance product offerings. Find new product combinations that appeal to certain types of customers, which will boost sales and happiness.

Fine-tune marketing campaigns. Maximise the efficacy of marketing campaigns by tailoring messaging and targeting techniques to customer insights.

Adjust strategies. To make proactive changes to plans, it is necessary to evaluate market trends to spot new possibilities or dangers.

Case in point. A leading audit and consulting business hired Infopulse to build a financial analytics application that runs in real time. Infopulse allowed for data availability in near real-time and increased data processing speeds by as much as 100 times by migrating Finance databases to SAP HANA Advanced Financial Analytics and combining Special and General Ledger transactions. Over 10,000 daily users were empowered with advanced analytics capabilities and were able to make more informed strategic decisions because to this automation, which decreased human reporting requirements.

Business Process Automation

Among the technology priorities cited by 41% of respondents, the strategic use of data has the potential to greatly enhance operational efficiency and effectiveness. In financial institutions, where numerous repetitive tasks necessitate automation, this is of utmost importance. The banking industry can reap substantial benefits from integrating data analytics with business process automation because:

Automation Opportunities: Banks can successfully prioritise automation efforts by using data analysis to pinpoint repetitive, time-consuming processes. There may be bottlenecks and automatable regions that can be found in transaction logs, client interactions, and data from internal processes.

Enhanced Decision-Making: Analysing data yields priceless knowledge about consumer habits, industry tendencies, and potential dangers. Financial institutions can use this data to automate tasks like credit scoring, fraud detection, and individualised product suggestions.

Improved Customer Experience: automating routine tasks allows employees more time to provide individualised service to customers. While humans are free to deal with complicated problems and cultivate closer relationships, data-driven chatbots and virtual assistants can answer common requests.

Increased Compliance and Risk Management: As part of risk management, data analysis can be employed to spot patterns and outliers. To reduce financial losses and maximise regulatory compliance, automated systems can identify questionable activity and send it for additional inspection.

The data platform ensures that all required data is always accessible regardless of whether it is kept in the bank's internal databases or in other systems. When it comes to managing the customer experience and engaging with customers, this is a crucial element.

PERSONALIZED EXPERIENCES

One of the most significant competitive differentiators in the modern banking industry is the capacity to provide personalised experiences. There is a concerning lack of personalisation among 44% of customers, according to the World Retail Banking Report 2022. Data platforms should be seriously considered as part of the sales and marketing strategy's efforts to reach its target audience through new channels. In a poll conducted by McKinsey, it was found that while 71% of customers want firms to deliver them personalised encounters, 76% of those customers feel disappointed when their expectations aren't met. Businesses that have a higher return on investment from customisation also grow at a faster rate and it is shown in figure 4.

Fig 4: The Impact of Customer-Focused Approach on Company Performance

Platforms are increasingly transitioning to a role of supporting internet businesses. According to this theory, platforms can use GSM or GPS data to analyse consumer actions in near-real-time and use that information as needed. Sending a personalised offer for a car loan via the app or SMS immediately is worth it if the customer wants to visit a car dealership, for example. Banks can also give a credit programme and automatically offer to transfer payments in installments when a customer buys a TV. Put simply, the main goal of the platform is to keep track of the client's desires and interests so that the relevant offer is either promptly delivered or, failing that, may be anticipated.

CONCLUSION

The requirement for a data platform that can assist financial institutions in realising the full potential of their investments in information technology and data has become more crucial than it has ever been. To summarise everything, we can say that it is today hard to conceive of an organisation that does not possess a contemporary cloud data platform that is capable of replacing the majority of the human work (such as generating reports, calculating various indicators, and analysing the information that is provided) with the platform. Businesses can combine several systems and establish a unified environment with the assistance of data platforms, which allows them to manage all their data in a one location. They can obtain insights into the behaviour of their customers and make better judgements in a timely manner because of this.

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